

A Study on Local Wisdom towards Career Building of People in Kamchanoad Community

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Abstract—This research gathered local wisdom towards career building of people in Kamchanoad Community, Baan Muang sub-district, Baan Dung district, Udon Thani province. Data was collected through in-depth interviews with village headmen, community board, teachers, monks, Kamchanoad forest managers and revered elderly aged over 60 years old. All of these 30 interviewees have resided in Kamchanoad Community for more than 40. Descriptive data analysis result revealed that the most prominent local wisdom of Kamchanoad community is their beliefs and religion. Most people in the community have strongly maintained local tradition, the festival of appeasing Chao Pu Sri Suttho on the middle of the 6th month of Thai lunar calendar which falls on the same day with Vesak Day. 100 percent of the people in this community are Buddhist. They believe that Naga, an entity or being, taking the form of a serpent, named “Sri Suttho” lives in Kamchanoad forest. The local people worship the serpent and ask for blessings. Another local wisdom of this community is Sinh fabric weaving.

Keywords—Local Wisdom, Careers, Kamchanoad Community.

I. INTRODUCTION

LOCAL wisdom is “The knowledge that discovered or acquired by local people through the accumulation of experiences in trials and integrated with the understanding of surrounding nature and culture.” [1] Local wisdom is fundamental, not only represents the Thainess, but also an important tool in developing countries in various areas. The excessive favor towards foreign wisdom over the local wisdom often brings problems to development. Understanding the roots of local wisdom creates pride in the national heritage. [2] Thus, local wisdoms are associated with the nature of each community. They are adjusted to suit the environment and context of each community over time, and have developed and have been inherited for a long time. So there is an important connection between knowledge and professional, economic, well-being, spending, educational and cultural aspects. Reference [3] indicated that, for each community in Thailand, there is much wisdom used to cherish the lifestyle of the people to live peacefully and help solve the crisis to pass. The local wisdom includes parts of the culture that are knowledge, way of thinking, ability, opinion, belief, wisdom with respect to housing, livelihood, lifestyle, disease prevention, and the

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use of language. All of these that have been continuously accumulated developed, utilized and transmitted since the ancient time. [4] The modifications to the invention combined with new knowledge and developed to improve the quality of life in the community and adaptation to suit the changing context of society. [5] The importance of local knowledge is an important issue in research to further develop the needs of the local people. The researchers defined the research area at Kamchanoad Community, Baan Muang sub-district, Baan Dung district, Udon Thani province located in the northeast of Thailand. The highlights are Chanoad trees that resemble an island in the middle of the field. People are bound to believe the serpent and mysterious stories that happened in the community that have been told from generation to generation, as well as praying to Chao Pu Sri Sutth (Naga) for comfort and fortune. Kamchanoad community also has Sinh fabric weaving. Some local wisdom are being forgotten. This is due to factors like economic, political and social factors. These factors have resulted in the lifestyle of the community change. People were immigrating to the city leaving only the elderly who have no income, no career, nor hobby [6] The wave of community development has caused social and economic structural changes which resulted in young people in the community turning to become a laborer in the big cities, leaving children to their parents. This makes them the lack of opportunity to learn and inherit a unique local community. Most elderly people in the community’s primary role is raising children instead giving knowledge as a local guru. [7] Therefore, the researchers aim to integrate the career building with local knowledge to achieve awareness for conservation and to encourage people in Kamchanoad community with quality living.

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of this research was to study each person in Urban communities about activities with reference to Philosophy of Sufficiency Economy and to understand how to application in any level of individual and household.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The target group of this research is the population of Kamchanoad Community (Baan Non Muang) Baan Muang sub-district, Baan Dung district, Udon Thani province that are community leaders such as village headmen, community board, teachers, monks, Kamchanoad forest managers and revered elderly aged over 60 years old. The researchers have chosen key informants according to these criteria:

1. Informants who play a role related to the promotion and dissemination of local knowledge.
2. Informants who have professional or experience by inventing themselves, and have been living in the community for a period of 40 years or more.

There are 30 key informants consisted of 1 village headman, 5 community board members, 1 teacher, 3 monks, and 20 revered elderly aged over 60 years old. Data were collected by semi-structure interview. There are 5 main issues. 1) Traditions and religious beliefs 2) Language and Literature 3) Art and Archaeology, 4) Music and recreation, 5) Life and Science. Content Analysis was conducted.

IV. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

The local wisdom of Kamchanoad Community (Baan Non Muang) Baan Muang sub-district, Baan Dung district, Udon Thani province that is most prominent is Traditions and religious beliefs. Most people in the community have strongly maintained local tradition, the festival of appeasing Chao Pu Sri Suttho on the middle of the 6th month of Thai lunar calendar with Vesak Day. 100 percent of the people in this community are Buddhist. They believe that Naga, an entity or being, taking the form of a serpent, named "Sri Suttho" lives in Kamchanoad forest. The local people worship the serpent and ask for blessings.

From past to present, all the local residents hold their faith and it becomes even stronger as is evident from the Songkran festival when people from all over the country flocked to pray for peace throughout as shown in the following figures.

Fig. 1 Patting gong for fortune

Fig. 2 The Statue of Chao Pu Sri Suttho

Fig. 3 Chanoad tree

Fig. 4 Chanoad tree

Fig. 5 Holy well

Fig. 6 Songkran festival in 2557

Fig. 9 Preparation of Sinh fabric weaving

Fig. 7 Kamchanoad forest

For language and literature aspect, everyone uses Isan dialect (northeastern dialect). For arts and archeology, there are no clear activities reflecting the local culture. For music and recreation, there is a local folk band and the cinematography at least 3-2times a month. The authority has set the Kamchanoad forest to be the new tourist destination of Udon Thani province. Lastly, for life and science, people are not poor. Many of them do some farming as the main occupation. On the side, they grow marigolds flowers for tourists to buy to appease Chao Pu Sri Suttho. Many families open stores in the area of the island of Kamchanoad forest.

Apart from the beliefs, another local wisdom of this community is Sinh fabric weaving. Currently, there is only Mrs. Samorn Khantikul, 76, who carries this knowledge. In the past, the fabric was intended for use in religious traditions, but in modern society most people in the community want to wear something more comfortable like pants instead of sarongs or Sinh skirts.

Fig. 10 Sinh fabric weaving

Fig. 11 Mat weaving

Fig. 8 Sinh fabric pattern

Fig. 12 Mat weaving with Kamchanoad pattern

V. CONCLUSION/ DISCUSSION

Local knowledge can create a unique career-building opportunity and promote jobs for the public if it is applied or integrated accordingly. The local wisdom is also an important foundation for sustainable social development. Social issues can be resolved. The knowledge should be recognized by every community and be used for the benefit of their family, community, society, and nation. Kamchanoad Community, Baan Muang sub-district, Baan Dung district, Udon Thani province is looking for its uniqueness that will create value for local people that everyone in this generation can understand and then develop themselves and create sustainability for generations to come and cherish the wisdom. The local wisdom can create jobs to the community. As a result, the residents will not have to leave their home to become laborers in the capital city. Findings have shown that long-term community development leads to job creation and income generation for the elderly in Baan Non Muang Community, Baan Muang sub-district, Baan Dung district, Udon Thani province. The leader and people partnership and participation is an important factor of development in community. Community leaders have participation with the community as much, community development even more. Point out that the harmony arising from the inside community, to participate in the community, the higher would be the measure of the sustainable development of the community in a positive direction as well [8].

VI. SUGGESTIONS

Local government and private sector agencies in Baan Muang sub-district, Baan Dung district, Udon Thani province should engage with people in the community in delivering the knowledge to learn the local knowledge of local scholars. A systematic data collection and support of the exchange of experiences with people in the community directly are needed. Furthermore, creating network to link and transmit as well as joining forces to develop local wisdom are crucial to establishing the identity of the community into a center of learning, research and community outreach.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by Institute for Research and Development, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University (www.ssru.ac.th); especially, the generosity and guidance systematically from all lecturers and staff in SSRU were highly appreciated.

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